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D4.1: Single-Channels Tests, Results and Analysis

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Abstract

The WP4 is dedicated to the Realization of aerothermal and mechanical tests of elementary component of the CHX on dedicated test facilities by means of advanced measurement techniques. This first report D4.1 summarizes the work done on the tasks T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 dedicated to the measurements of the single channel elements. The first task consisted in designing the facility dedicated to aerothermal measurements to be performed on single-channel modules. The second task consisted in instrumenting the single channels. The focus was on measuring inlet temperature, outlet temperature profiles, temperature and pressure evolution along the channel length. Finally, the third task consisted in performing the experimental tests on the single channel modules. Originally 20 single element modules were planned to test the surface finish, the effect of texture design, the influence of the fin design, the channel design, and the effect of cross-section variation. Finally, 17 samples were tested. More details on the different elements can be found in deliverables D3.1: 3D sample, structure design report, D3.2: 3D samples, manufacturing conformity report, and D3.3: 3D samples, design and manufacturing report. For all tests, experimental data were processed and analyzed. Correlations of pressure drops and convective heat transfer coefficients were established. In this report, discussions about non-dimensional forms of the pressure drop (i.e. Fanning factor) and the heat transfer coefficient (Nusselt, Colburn), as well as the goodness factor are helping in the comparison of the different geometries.

The deliverable was originally planned at M18 but as T4.3 ended in M25, it was more logical to delay the delivery of the report to M25 as well. A few weeks delay are to be observed for this report due to late delivery of the single elements V9, V10 and N10 (March 2nd), as well as covid-19.

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1. Introduction

The WP4 is dedicated to the Realization of aerothermal and mechanical tests of elementary component of the CHX on dedicated test facilities by means of advanced measurement techniques. Two main facilities will be designed to test two types of elementary components: single channel elements, and combined hot-cold elements.

This report summarizes the work done on the tasks T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 dedicated to the measurements of the single channel elements. The first task consisted in designing the facility dedicated to aerothermal measurements to be performed on single-channel modules. The second task consisted in instrumenting the single channels. The focus was on measuring inlet temperature, outlet temperature profiles, temperature and pressure evolution along the channel length. Finally, the third task consisted in performing the experimental tests on the single channel modules. Originally 20 single element modules were planned to test the surface finish, the effect of texture design, the influence of the fin design, the channel design, and the effect of cross-section variation. For all tests, experimental data were processed and analyzed. Correlations of pressure drop, convective heat transfer coefficient was established. Validation of CFD prediction is also performed [16].

The second chapter details the experimental facility as well as the instrumentation used. A list of all elements printed, instrumented, and tested is also provided. More details on the different elements can be found in deliverables D3.1: 3D sample, structure design report, D3.2: 3D samples, manufacturing conformity report, and D3.3: 3D samples, design and manufacturing report. The third chapter details all aerodynamic measurements such as inlet and outlet velocity profiles, as well as pressure drop in his dimensional and non-dimensional form (Fanning factor). Further analysis of the fanning factor allowed a determination of a theoretical roughness, compared with the measured roughness. The fourth chapter details all thermal measurements such as outlet temperature profiles, bottom wall temperature contours, fluid temperature evolution. The chapter also proposes a definition for the heat transfer coefficient and proposes a non-dimensional analysis through the Colburn factor. This factor is also compared to the Fanning for a complete comparison of the different tested geometries. Finally, the last chapter provides conclusions that will help the measurements of the hot-cold elements.

2. Experimental Setup

The facility used for testing has been designed and developed at the VKI laboratories. The most changeable aspect of the experimental investigation is to perform both flow aerualics and thermal measurements inside different designs of CHX modules, because of the reduced dimensions of the samples. The pressure has been monitored using pressure taps located along the sample. The characterization of the thermal flow properties has been performed using thermocouples probes for gas temperature measurements and the IR camera to monitor the temperature distribution along the bottom wall. An electric resistance, located on the top of the CHX module, provides heat through Joule effect. The hot-wire probe has been exploited to perform velocity measurements at the inlet and outlet sections of a selection of samples. In the proposal, the facility needed to require the following: Reynolds on the channel hydraulic diameter ranging from 400 to 1000.

2.1 Facility design

The facility has been designed and assembled at the VKI. Figure 2.1 shows a schematic of the main components of the set-up. Compressed air from the 7 bar line supplies the facility through a flexible pipe. The mass flow is regulated using three rotameters (YOKOGAWA) in an available range up to 30 g/s. A divergent is used as a connection to a rectangular cross section metallic pipe, which is directly connected to the test section. Downstream of the divergent, a bronze porous plate is installed to guarantee a uniform ow in the test section. The length of the connecting metallic pipe has been settled, in the design phase, to ensure a fully developed velocity profile at the inlet of the test section. The region from the pipe inlet to the point at which the velocity profile is fully developed is called the hydrodynamic entrance region, and the length of this region is called the hydrodynamic entry length L_h . First preliminary calculations have been performed to define the flow regime in the inlet rectangular section. As the flow is turbulent in all the possible ranges of mass flow rates, the length of the pipe downstream the porous media has been retrieved from the correlation for fully developed turbulent flow [1]:

$$L_h = 1.359 D_h Re^{1/4}$$

Considering the dimensions of the rectangular pipe equal to 50 mm x 15 mm, the designed hydraulic diameter is equal to 23 mm, hence $L = 32 D_h = 736$ mm. The first design foresaw the porous media located between two sections in which the metallic pipe is divided(number 8 in Figure 1). However, the hot-wire analysis of the velocity profile at the inlet section of the CHX module has shown a not fully developed velocity profile. Hence, different configurations have

been tested to define the best location of the porous media. As final location it has been installed after the divergent, as it is assuring a more symmetrical velocity profile.

- | | |
|----------------------------|------------------|
| 1. Inlet | 6. Flexible pipe |
| 2. Compress air | 7. Divergent |
| 3. Valve regulating system | 8. Metallic pipe |
| 4. Flexible pipe | 9. CHX module |
| 5. Rotameters | 10. Outlet |

Figure 1 : Schematic of the facility

Figure 2 shows a picture of the entire facility set-up.

Figure 2 Complete setup of the facility

2.1. Single-channel elements

The test section consists of the CHX module instrumented with the probes needed for its thermal and aeraulic characterization. The 3D printed samples tested during the experimental campaign have the same internal geometry, but one is in Aluminum alloy and the other is in Nickel alloy to investigate on the influence of the material on the thermal performances. Briefly, the main properties of these two materials are described as follows:

- AS7G06: aerospace Aluminum alloy with low weight, high resistance to corrosion and excellent heat and electricity conduction.
- Inconel 718 (IN718): aerospace nickel-based super-alloy with good resistance to oxidation, corrosion and high strength in temperature ranges from cryogenic up to ≈ 1000 K.

Its external dimensions are 52 mm \times 17 mm \times 120 mm and the fins occupy an effective length equal to 100 mm. The external wall thickness is 1 mm. All elementary channels have an inlet cross section. However, the channels 7, 9, and 10 see their cross-section reduced along the channel length. The Table 1 summarizes the tested geometries, providing their name, the material, the type of internal structure, the printing direction, as well as if the elementary channel had a constant cross section or not. A more detailed configuration of the test matrix is provided in the section 2.4: testing conditions.

Table 1 Summary of tested geometries

Material	Name	Elementary structure	Printing information	Cst cross section
Inconel 718	N1	offset-strip	45° Horizontal	Y
Inconel 718	N1b	offset-strip	45° Horizontal (10°XY)	Y
Inconel 718	N2	M	Vertical (Z)	Y
Inconel 718	N3	M	Vertical (Z)	Y
Inconel 718	N5	X-Opt.	Vertical (Z)	Y
Inconel 718	N6	Giroid	Vertical (Z)	Y
Inconel 718	N7	Evolutive thickness	45° Horizontal	N
Inconel 718	N9	Hot	Vertical (Z)	N
Inconel 718	N10	Cold	Vertical (Z)	N
AS07	V1	offset-strip	45° Horizontal	Y
AS07	V4_1	M	Vertical (Z)	Y
AS07	V4_2	M	Vertical (Z)	Y

AS07	V5	X-Opt.	Vertical (Z)	Y
AS07	V6	Giroid	Vertical (Z)	Y
AS07	V7	Evolutive thickness	45° Horizontal	N
AS07	V9	Hot	Vertical (Z)	N
AS07	V10	Cold	Vertical (Z)	N

2.2. Instrumentation

Figure 3 shows a schematic of the instrumented test section used for the measurements. The measurements consist mainly in pressure drop measurements and temperature measurements.

Figure 3 Schematic of the test section

The pressure drop along the sample is monitored using a row of five pressure taps with a 0.4 mm diameter located on one side of the channel. The pressure difference between each pressure tap is measured using a pressure transducer. The differences in internal geometries

showed a large span of pressure range encountered. Therefore, the maximum pressure sensitivity of the membranes used for pressure measurements varied with the tests, and are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Max. pressure of membranes used for pressure measurements

Geometries	Material	Membrane max. Pressure [Pa]
1,2,3,5,6	Aluminum, Inconel	2070
7	Aluminum, Inconel	5500
9,10	Aluminum, Inconel	10 340 and 20 680

For temperature measurement, type-K thermocouples from omega are used. The thermocouple wires are 0.08mm in diameter, insulated in PFA, with an exposed junction. The thermocouples are then inserted in the test sample, or positioned in a home-made rake by VKI technical personnel. The inlet air temperature is measured using a rake of four type-K thermocouples, located one on each side of the inlet rectangular cross section. The outlet temperature is monitored using nine thermocouples type K, positioned on a cross shaped rake. A row of five thermocouples type K is located along the CHX module, on the opposite side of the pressure taps, to detect the temperature of the flow blown inside the channel during the test. A heating plate in Copper, of 0.2 mm thickness, is glued on the top side of the CHX sample. Supplied by a DC generator, it provides heat, through Joule effect, to the air flowing inside the sample. Its dimensions are 50mmx100 mm to cover all the length occupied by the fins in the sample. The plate is fixed on the module using a very high conductivity paste OMEGA™ 201, to reduce a possible effect of the contact resistance. The temperature of the wall in contact with the heating plate is measured using a raw of five type-K thermocouples glued on the top wall of the sample. Insulation has been adopted to cover the CHX element on the sides and the top wall to make negligible any effect of heat dispersion by both radiation and natural convection with the ambient. The IR camera is used as a non-intrusive measurement technique to study the temperature distribution over the bottom surface of the sample and that proved to be efficient for complex fluid flow configurations [2]. Pictures of the instrumentation can be observed in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4 Instrumentation: Inlet and outlet rakes as well as close up view of test section

Figure 5 Instrumented CHX module

Concerning the Data Acquisition system, the measurements from the thermocouples and the pressure tap are acquired using the NI cDAQ 9174 four modules acquisition board, where there are plugged:

- Two modules NI 9213 with 16 channels each for the temperature acquisition;
- One module NI 9205 with 16 channels for the voltage data acquisition from the pressure taps;

All the data are collected using the LabVIEW software NI Signal Express 2005.

The thermocouples installed on the inlet and outlet rakes were calibrated by using an ageing chamber Weiss WK L34/40. The calibration of the rakes consists in comparing the temperature values measured by the modules NI 9213 with the reference probe value since the modules are already equipped with a cold-junction sensor compensating for the temperature differences between the channels of the terminal, due to thermal gradients across the acquisition module. Seventeen calibration measurements were acquired for these thermocouples every 5°C from 10°C to 90°C. The reference temperature inside the chamber was acquired by mean of a PT100 probe of class 1/3 ($\pm 0.08^\circ\text{C}$ at 0°C) with a number model PL1/3M30-300 of omega. The signal from this probe was transferred to a NI9217 card for acquisition at a frequency of 10 Hz and for a duration of 20 s, for a total of 200 samples for each measurement. The uncertainties associated to these measurements are developed in §6.4.1 Due to possible inhomogeneous temperature distribution inside the chamber, the calibration measurements were achieved twice with two different positions of the rakes, to verify the impact of those positions on the calibration curve. The analysis of the calibration curves for the two positions showed very little difference, below the uncertainty of $\pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$ associated to these temperature measurements (§ 6.4.1). An example of the calibration curves obtained for the outlet rake thermocouples is shown on Figure 6. As can be noticed, the trend of the curve is very linear with almost no offset, especially for the first measurement points that are perfectly aligned on the fitting trend.

Figure 6: Outlet rake thermocouples calibration curves

Velocity profile measurements at the inlet and outlet sections of the CHX module have been performed using a constant temperature hot wire probe with a Tungsten wire. The probe was placed in the middle of the cross-section of the channel and moved vertically by a transverse system, with a 0.2 mm spatial resolution. The acquisition frequency was set to 25 kHz. As this kind of probe is very sensitive to the temperature alterations, the procedure described by Baldani et al. [17] was adopted for the temperature correction. A schematic of the experimental setup used for these measurements can be observed in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Velocity measurement experimental setup

Roughness measurements on all the samples have been achieved using the surface roughness meter MITUTOYO SurfTest SJ 201P. This instrument is able to measure several parameters like the R_z (maximum height of the profile) or the R_a (arithmetical mean deviation). In the present study, the R_a was measured, which is a widely used parameter. It was noticed during the measurements that the heat exchanger modules roughness was differing not only between the inner bottom and top surfaces, but also between the inlet and outlet sides. Thereby, the average roughness at these four surfaces was measured for each sample by acquiring a minimum of 10 points and calculating the averaged value. Then the overall roughness was obtained by averaging the averaged roughness at the four positions.

The tables 3 and 4 below present the overall roughness value for every Inconel and Aluminum samples.

	N1	N1b	N2	N3	N5	N6	N7	N9	N10
Ra (μm)	13.1	16.6	5.8	8.5	9.8	8.8	9.7	6.0	7.4

Table 3: Inconel sample roughness

	V1	V41	V42	V5	V6	V7	V9	V10
Ra (μm)	27.1	10.2	10.9	10.7	9.9	13.6	11.8	10.5

Table 4: Aluminum sample roughness

It can be noticed that for equivalent geometries, the Aluminum samples show from a slightly higher to a much higher roughness than the Inconel ones. The highest roughness is found for both cases with the geometry 1. The other geometries present a quite similar roughness for a given material.

2.3. Testing conditions

The experimental campaign has been led in the same working conditions all samples. The operating mass flow range is up to 20 g/s. For the thermal analysis, the heating plate supplied a constant Joule power equal to 130 W. The pressure was measured at ambient temperature to neglect the influence of the temperature in the air density. The pressure measurements were always performed by steps of 2g/s from 0 to 20 g/s. The minimal flow range used for thermal measurements varied from 2 to 7 g/s. Indeed, especially for Inconel samples, when the forced convection induced by the air was not sufficient to evacuate the heat provided by Joule effect, overheating of the resistance was observed and potential damages of the element. A summary of the testing conditions is provided in Table 5.

Table 5 Experimental test matrix

Geometry	U	ΔP	T	Ra
1	[5:5:20] g/s	[0:1:20] g/s	[3:1:20] g/s	Y
1 bis	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[7:1:20] g/s	Y
2	-	[0:1:20] g/s	[3:1:20] g/s	Y
3 (a)	-	[0:1:20] g/s	[3:1:20] g/s	Y
5	-	[0:1:20] g/s	[7:1:20] g/s	Y
6	-	[0:1:20] g/s	[3:1:20] g/s	Y

7	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[10:1:20] g/s	Y
9	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[10:1:20] g/s	Y
10	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[10:1:20] g/s	Y
1	[5:5:20] g/s	[0:1:20] g/s	[3:1:20] g/s	Y
4 (1)	10 g/s	[0:1:20] g/s	[4:1:20] g/s	Y
4 (1,2)	10 g/s	[0:1:20] g/s	[4:1:20] g/s	Y
5	10 g/s	[0:1:20] g/s	[4:1:20] g/s	Y
6	10 g/s	[5:1:20] g/s	[5:1:20] g/s	Y
7	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[5:1:20] g/s	Y
9	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[5:1:20] g/s	Y
10	-	[0:2:20] g/s	[5:1:20] g/s	Y

2.4. Measurement uncertainty

Before the analysis of the results, it is important to give an estimation of the uncertainties linked to the measurements. These uncertainties depend on several factors such as the statistical independency of the samples, the material used to acquire the signal or even the minimum accuracy at which the mass-flow can be set. These contributions and their calculations are developed in §6. Table 6 shortly lists the uncertainties associated to the main quantities of interest in the present study, within a confidence interval of 95%.

Property	Uncertainty
\dot{m}	± 0.15 g/s
Δp	± 219.84 to ± 2069.6 Pa
$T_{\text{thermocouple}}$	± 0.6 °C
T_{IRcamera}	± 1.2 °C
u	± 0.3 m/s

Table 6: Uncertainty evaluation of the main measured quantities

3. Aeraulic measurements

The section focuses on the aeraulic characterization of all the samples listed above in the table 5. When passing through the sample, the airflow undergoes friction losses due to friction at the wall, as well as obstacles and change of direction. Ideally, the CHX module has to create as less losses as possible. The total pressure drops were obtained by the addition of the pressure differences measured by the five pressure taps as described in 2.2. In a first time, an example of the pressure evolution and distribution along a sample is described in 3.1. In a

second time, the sensitivity analysis performed is explained in 3.2. It was performed to assess the impact of the outlet rake and of the heat addition on the friction losses. Then all the samples were tested and the pressure drops for the range of air mass flow like described in 2.3 were measured. The results for all the configurations are compared in 3.3., and are compared in their non-dimensional form in 3.4.

3.1. Pressure evolution

As explained in section 2.3, the samples were tested at a mass-flow range varying from 2g/s to 20g/s by steps of 2g/s, and the measurements were acquired during 20s at a frequency of 10Hz. Since the modules show roughness differences depending on the material, the total pressure drop in the channel is expected to be different for each material for one given CHX geometry. The total pressure drop through a sample is defined as the pressure difference between the first pressure tap and the atmospheric pressure. Since the pressure difference at low mass-flow could be very low, it was important to use an atmospheric pressure as accurate as possible in the post-processing. Thus, the pressure of the surrounding was acquired at every mass-flow tested.

The figure 8 show the trend of the total pressure drop along the channel as function of the mass-flow, for the geometry 1 and for the Aluminum and Inconel modules respectively. The experimental results have been fitted with a power law assuming a confidence interval of 95%. The results for every CHX sample are presented later on in the section 3.3.

a) Aluminum CHX module (V1)

b) Inconel CHX module (N1)

Figure 8: Total pressure drop along the Inconel CHX module of geometry 1 (N1)

As predictable, the Aluminum sample presents higher pressure drops than the Inconel for the same range of Reynolds number. As the mass flow rate increases, the difference grows, and reaches a percentage of difference around 20% at 20g/s as shown on figure 9. This effect is due to the surface finish which is the only main difference between the two samples, as they have the same internal geometry.

As one could have guessed, the pressure drop increases with the mass flow. For a constant cross-section area, higher mass flow implies a rise of the flow velocity in the fins passages; according to Bernoulli equations, as the total energy of the flow is constant, an increase of the flow velocity means a reduction of the static pressure of the fluid, generating higher energy losses. The uncertainty associated with these measurements is equal to +/-218:4Pa, in a confidence interval of 95%.

Figure 9: Percentage of the pressure drop increase in Aluminium channel with respect to the Inconel, Channel 1

For a further insight of the local pressure drop inside the channel, the pressure drop between each pressure tap has been analyzed for four different mass flow rates: 5 g/s; 10 g/s; 15 g/s and 20 g/s, to observe the effect of the mass flow. Figure 10 shows these trends for the geometry 1, and for both Aluminum and Inconel samples (V1 and N1). It can be observed that the pressure drop is not the same between each pressure tap present in the channel; in particular, it is higher for the first three taps and it shows a linear trend; the last one is lower, followed by the pressure drop to the atmospheric pressure, which can be considered constant for all the cases. This behavior can be easily explained considering the location of the pressure taps. The last two pressure taps are closer than the previous three and this justifies the lower value of pressure drop obtained in this last section. As the mass flow increases, the pressure drop in this last section is lower in a higher percentage than the other two previous contributions along the sample. Hence the trend appears less linear than the one obtained for low flow rate.

a) Aluminum CHX module (V1)

b) Inconel CHX module (N1)

Figure 10: Local pressure drop along the samples for four mass-flow rates, for the geometry 1 and for both materials

The same observations can be done considering Fig. 12, which represents the weights of each pressure drop between two pressure taps for all the tested mass flow rates. The trend is not linear for any of them and it is increasing with the mass flow. Moreover, due to the geometrical location of the probes, the highest pressure drops are always measured between the three first taps.

a) Aluminum CHX module (V1)

b) Inconel CHX module (N1)

Figure 11: Contribution of the different local pressure drops along the samples for both materials

One last consideration can be made. Even though the total pressure drop through the samples of geometry 1 is differing between Aluminum and Inconel, it can be noticed that their trends of the contribution of the local pressure drops are very similar. The first three taps have the

highest contribution to the overall pressure drop for both materials. It means that although the surface finish has a high impact on the pressure drop, the shape of the geometry itself is driving the repartition of the pressure drops along the sample and the contribution of the different pressure taps.

3.1.1. Sensitivity analysis

The effect of two parameters on the pressure drop measurement was studied. The first one was the presence of the outlet thermocouples rake. Given the diameter of the horizontal tube compared to the outlet sample section ($\sim 1/10$), measurements with and without this rake were conducted on sample N1b, to make sure that it was not creating a blockage effect, and thus not impacting the airflow. The second parameter was the impact on the pressure drops of the heating of the sample and so of the air flowing through the sample. Indeed, the aerualic characterization of the samples were conducted without heat since the assumption was taken that for the range of Reynolds number studied, the influence of heating up the airflow and thus accelerating the fluid was negligible. However, this had to be confirmed with some measurements.

The figure 13 below show, for the Inconel sample 1b (N1b), the results in terms of total pressure drops respectively without and without the outlet rake, and with and without heating the sample.

Figure 12: Total pressure drops for the N1b sample with and without rake, as well as with or without heat addition

As can be noticed, the influence of the outlet rake on the pressure drops, and so on the airflow, is up to 150 Pa which is inferior to the uncertainty of ± 218.4 Pa associated to these measurements. Thereby, the influence of the outlet rake seems negligible. The addition of

heat to the system increases the pressure drops created in the air as one can expect. However, the same way as for the outlet rake, for the range of mass flow considered, the increase remains in the uncertainty of the friction losses measured. Since the difference between the two curves tends to increase, it can be concluded that the assumption taken about the negligible impact on the pressure drops of heat addition to air for the considered mass flow is correct. Nevertheless, it seems that for higher mass flow tested, some attention will have to be paid on that point.

3.1.2. Comparison of configurations

Nine configurations of Inconel samples and eight configurations of Aluminum samples were tested. As a reminder, it is recalled that the total pressure drop through each sample was obtained by adding the five differential pressure drops measured from the taps and the atmospheric pressure. However, the outlet cross-section is not constant for every geometry. As a matter of fact, the geometries 9 and 10 have smaller outlet cross-section than the other samples, and the geometry 7 has a non-constant cross-section, increasing along the inlet-outlet axis of the heat exchanger. Though, for sake of simplicity, the size of all the samples inlet flange was kept constant to avoid making different sets of rectangular channels providing the airflow. As a consequence, the geometries 7, 9 and 10 present a converging shape before the fins part, which creates a non-negligible singular pressure drop. However, the interesting pressure drop for the comparison of the samples altogether concerns the losses created by the fins. It means that only the pressure drops between the pressure taps were considered for the comparison and divided by the total distance between the taps, as shown in Figure 13.

For all geometries except 7, the outer section containing the fins is constant through all the fin arrangement. Therefore, the static pressure difference is equal to the total pressure difference. This definition excludes the pressure drop due to the entrance effects as well as the pressure drop due to exit effects, which is not relevant as the real interest consists in the pressure drop inside the fins.

Figure 13 Linear pressure drop definition

For the geometries N7 and V7, the outer test section has a constant width of 50 mm, but the height evolves linearly between point 1 and point 5, with a height varying from 4mm to 8 mm. Therefore, the static pressure difference here does not represent the total pressure difference. For this geometry, the dynamic pressure was added, calculated as follow:

$$v_2 = \frac{A_1}{A_2} v_1$$

$$\Delta P_{tot} = \Delta P_{static} + \frac{1}{2} \rho (v_1^2 - v_2^2)$$

The figure 14 below shows the linear friction losses for every configuration, for respectively the Aluminum and Inconel samples. These linear drops give an indication of the amount of pressure lost when the air passes across the fins, per length considered.

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 14: Linear pressure drops from taps 2 to 5 across every samples

As one could expect, Aluminum CHX geometries generally show for their equivalent geometries made with Inconel, higher total pressure drops, except for geometries 9 and 10. Besides the order for the first four geometries in terms of pressure drops, remains the same for both materials: $N5 < N2/3 < N1/1b$ and $V5 < V4_1/4_2 < V1$. It can also be noticed that the Inconel geometry N1b creates equivalent pressure drops as N1, whereas it presents higher roughness.

Another relevant fact to notice is that the geometry 5 has almost the same delta P for both materials because the roughness of the samples is quite equivalent between Aluminum and Inconel. The same conclusion can be drawn for geometry 6.

However, the geometry 7 presents higher pressure drops for the Aluminum CHX module than the Inconel one, which is consistent with the difference of roughness (R_a Aluminum is equal to $1.4 \times R_a$ of Inconel).

The geometries 9 and 10 show different behaviors because the sections does not have the same value between V9 and N9, and between V10 and N10. Indeed, although the roughness of the Inconel CHX modules is smaller than Aluminum, the pressure drops created by N9 and N10 are much higher than their equivalent geometry made with Aluminum. This is due to the fact that the flow cross-section is smaller for the Inconel sample N9, and that the fin density is higher for N10 than their equivalent Aluminum samples.

As in 3.1, it is interesting to have a closer look at how the evolution of the pressure inside the different channels for different mass-flows: 6 g/s, 10g/s and 16g/s (Fig. 15).

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 15: Pressure evolution along the sample for every sample

Apart from the geometry 6 that shows one small inflexion point, every geometry create pressure drops from the tap1 to 5, thus across their fins, that present very linear trends. Since the inflexion that can be seen at the tap 2 of the geometry 6 is found for both materials, it seems reasonable to link it to the shape of the fins. It may come from a local higher density of fins between the tap 1 and 2 that create relatively higher pressure drops than between the following taps.

Another fact is relevant to analyze. The geometries 9 and 10 present for both materials a negative value for the tap 5. This is due to a diffusive effect. Those geometries happen to have a quite high density of fins. Thus at the end of the CHX module, when the fin section ends, the fluid section passage becomes suddenly higher, creating a decrease of the velocity, and thus a negative difference of the static pressure. As can be seen on the Figure 15, this diffusive effect increases as the mass flow increases because the velocity inside the fins rises and so does the velocity difference. This effect is particularly noticeable on these geometries rather than on the others, because they have a denser section of fins when compared to the other samples.

3.1.3. Non-dimensional analysis and roughness effects

The pressure losses shown previously on figure 14 were adimensionnalized into the Fanning friction factor which represents the ratio between the shear stress at the wall and the kinetic energy of the fluid:

$$f_F = \frac{\Delta P \cdot D_h}{2\rho v^2 L}$$

Since some geometry, like N6 and V6, present quite internal complex shapes, it was difficult to use the usual definitions of the hydraulic diameter that relates the perimeter and cross-sectional area. Thereby, the following definition that relates the fluid volume over the heat exchange area was chosen:

$$D_h = \frac{V_{fluid}}{A_{exch}}$$

The values of all the hydraulic diameters calculated for the tested geometries are given in table 7, as well as the corresponding heat exchange area. Knowing the fluid volume and the total volume of each CHX modules, it was possible to calculate each corresponding porosity.

The Fanning factors were plotted as a function of the Reynolds number which is classically defined for flows in a pipes or tubes as:

$$Re = \frac{\rho v D_h}{\nu}$$

Where the velocity is taken to be the inlet velocity of the sample.

$$v = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho A_{inlet}}$$

For the inlet section, the width is similar for all samples and equal to 50mm, but the height differs from 1 geometry to another. A summary of the different channel heights (a value) at the locations of the fins is provided also in Table 7.

	V1	V4 ₁	V4 ₂	V5	V6	V7	V9	V10
Dh (mm)	1.05	1.44	1.45	1.32	0.599	0.788	0.622	1.15
Porosity	0.845	0.948	0.959	0.930	0.866	0.854	0.867	0.936
a (mm)	15	15	15	15	15	4-8	4.5	7.65

a) Aluminum CHX module

	N1	N1b	N2	N3	N5	N6	N7	N9	N10
Dh (mm)	1.05	1.05	1.35	1.35	1.32	0.599	0.788	0.533	0.977

Porosity	0.845	0.845	0.878	0.878	0.930	0.866	0.854	0.856	0.929
a (mm)	15	15	15	15	15	15	4-8	7	8

b) Inconel CHX module

Table 7: Porosity and hydraulic diameters for every sample

From the table 7 and the figure 16, it appears that the geometries V4₁-V4₂-V5 for Aluminum and N2-N3-N5 for Inconel have the highest value of hydraulic diameter, and they also create the lowest pressure drops (see Figure 12). On the other hand, the geometries 7 and 9 show the lowest hydraulic diameters, as well as the greatest pressure drops which is consistent. However, the order in the hydraulic diameter from the smallest to the greatest is not entirely consistent (Fig. 16) with the order of the curves (Fig. 12) from the lowest pressure drops created to the highest ones. It means that the friction losses through the samples cannot be related simply to the Dh value, but that the roughness of each sample plays an important role.

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 16: Pressure drops as a function of the hydraulic diameters of every sample

The same considerations can be done for the porosity (Fig 17). Indeed, the lower is the porosity, the higher are the pressure drops created through the samples. However, the order of the CHX modules presenting from the lowest to the highest porosity, is not matching perfectly the order of the curves of the pressure drops. Two geometries have a quite striking behaviour in terms of correlation between pressure drops and porosity. The geometry 1/1b has the lowest porosity of all the samples, while the geometry 10 shows a high porosity value. However, the CHX modules corresponding to these geometries for both materials create very similar and relatively high pressure drops (Fig. 12), while they show very different values of porosity.

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 17: Pressure drops as a function of the porosity of every sample

The Fanning friction factor for laminar flow of Newtonian fluids is generally calculated from the following law:

$$f_F = \frac{16}{Re} ; \text{for round tubes}$$

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 18: Fanning friction factors for both materials

The friction factor obtained from this law is plotted on the Figure 18 above. Even though in the laminar part of the curves, the friction factor of all the geometries does not overlap, especially in the case of Aluminum, the slope of their curve present a similar trend, for both materials that is in good agreement with the theory. Indeed, all the samples in the laminar part show a linear trend, followed by the transition part of the flow regime where all curves show an inflection and a minimum. The last part of the curve approaches the fully turbulent regime that is usually noticeable by a flattened trend, which is not reached though since the mass-flow rates tested are slightly too low. By taking into account through the Fanning factor, not only the pressure drops but also the hydraulic diameter, it appears that for both materials, the CHX modules N1/N1b and V1 present the highest factor. Indeed, since they also have the highest roughness, when compared to the other samples made of the same materials, and a medium value of hydraulic diameter, they have the largest ratio of roughness to hydraulic diameter. Concerning the geometries 7 and 9 for both Aluminum and Inconel, when their very high pressure drops are weighted by their low hydraulic diameter values, the resulting Fanning factors show relatively medium to low values. It means that in the ends these samples do not create so high friction losses when are also considered their geometric aspects. It should also be highlighted that all the Fanning factor values for every sample in the laminar part lies under the laminar part theory and fits better the laws $4/Re$, $5/Re$ and $10/Re$ that are plotted for indication (Fig. 18)

Another point is worth mentioning: the greatest is the friction factor; the smallest is the Reynolds number at which the fluid transitions from laminar to turbulent flow regime. For instance for Aluminum, the Reynolds number corresponding to this transition varies from 600 for V7 to 1700 for V5.

For turbulent flows, the laws relating the Darcy friction factor to the Reynolds number are more complex. The general correlation is given by the Colebrook equation [23]:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f_D}} = -2.0 \log \left(\frac{\varepsilon/D_h}{3.7} + \frac{2.51}{Re\sqrt{f_D}} \right)$$

Where ε/D_h is the relative roughness of the pipe. It is recalled that the Darcy friction factor is defined as four times the Fanning friction factor. Unfortunately, this formula is implicit. Several explicit developments exist. The explicit approximation developed by Stuart W. Churchill [18] cover both laminar and turbulent Reynolds numbers:

$$f_D = 8 \left(\left(\frac{8}{Re} \right)^{12} + (A + B)^{-1.5} \right)^{\frac{1}{12}} \text{ and } f_D = 4f_F$$

$$\text{Where } A = \left(2.457 \ln \left(\left(\left(\frac{7}{Re} \right)^{0.9} + 0.27 \frac{\varepsilon}{D_h} \right)^{-1} \right) \right)^{16}$$

$$\text{And } B = \left(\frac{37530}{Re} \right)^{16}$$

From the figure 18 and the equation above, a pipe relative roughness was evaluated for every sample, by fitting the part of the curves corresponding to the turbulent regime with a ε/D_h value. Since the plateau trend of the curve is not reached, normally corresponding to the fully developed turbulent regime, it should be noted that the relative roughness could be slightly underestimated.

Figure 19: Pipe relative roughness for every sample and comparison to literature values

The pipe relative roughness's evaluated for every sample (Fig. 19) show very similar behaviour to other studies of additively manufactured channels in the literature that have close values in terms of roughness R_a and hydraulic diameters to the value of the sample of the present work [6][21][22]. Indeed, as can be seen on Figure 19, they do not only show consistent values, but also a comparable trend: the pipe relative roughness is increasing linearly with a rise of

roughness-to-hydraulic diameter ratio. Some samples present much lower values of relative roughness (N5 & N7, V5, V7, V9 and V10). A piece of explanation for the geometries 5 and 7 could come from their very different features from the other samples. Indeed, the geometry 5 presents continuous fins unlike all the other geometries, which changes a lot the nature of the pressure drops created. The friction losses are of linear type, instead of being linear and singular like for the rest of the sample. Thus, the losses created are lower than a sample with interrupted fins, and the pipe relative roughness is also lower accordingly. Concerning the geometry 7, since it present a non-constant fluid section, and since the hydraulic diameter is calculated for a median section, the pipe relative roughness representative of the entire sample is hard to evaluate like for the other samples, which lead to a quite different value (Fig. 19).

3.2. Velocity profiles

This section focuses on the analysis of the vertical velocity profiles taken at the center of the test section. The first experimental matrix consists of measurements of the velocity profiles at the inlet section of the CHX module for four different mass flow rates: 5, 10, 15, and 20g/s. The same conditions were then used for the characterization of the outlet section velocity profiles for both the Aluminium and the Inconel CHX samples of geometry 1, and at the outlet of different geometries in Aluminium for 10g/s flow rate.

The results are investigating both the mean velocity and the turbulence intensity profiles. The turbulence intensity (TI) has been evaluated as the ratio between the standard deviation of the velocity fluctuations and the maximum velocity in the channel inlet section.

Figure 20 Velocity inlet profiles

Figure 20 left shows the mean inlet velocity profiles obtained for the different mass flow rates. The air flow velocity increases with the mass flow and the velocity profiles assume the typical shape of a fully developed pipe flow. The curves are symmetric: the velocity reaches a maximum value in correspondence of the channel axis, then it decreases in proximity of the upper and lower walls of the channel, because of the friction effect generated by the lateral sides. It must be highlighted that the velocity profiles have been corrected considering the effect of the temperature of the air flowing in the channel during the measurements, whose values are different from the conditions the hot-wire probe was calibrated. As this kind of probe is very sensible to the temperature alterations, the procedure described by Baldani et al. [17] was adopted for the temperature correction.

Figure 20 right shows the inlet turbulence intensity profiles obtained for the different mass flow rates. The trends appear symmetric with respect to the channel central axis for all the flow rates measured. All the plots have the same behavior: there is an increase of the TI in the near wall region followed by a rapid decay and a change of slope when going away from the wall until reaching the channel center. The rising of the TI in the near-wall region show that the turbulent actions are confined in the region adjacent to the walls: here, the low momentum fluid interacts with the regions at higher velocity, generating a momentum exchange of the fluid particles which initiate

turbulence in the form of longitudinal velocity fluctuations [19].

Figure 21 Inlet- Outlet profiles for the configuration 1 at 10g/s

The effect of the single channel element on the velocity and TI profiles is observed in Figure 21 for the configuration 1 in both Aluminum and Inconel. The velocity profiles appear flatter in the middle of the channel in both the cases and, for Inconel, the velocity values are always lower than the Aluminum. Regarding the TI, in both the cases, the same trend is obtained (Figure 21). It is possible to analyze the effect of the presence of the CHX on the TI levels: due to the tiny dimensions of the fins and their distance, the result of the presence of the CHX module can be treated as the one of a porous plate [12]. It straightens the flow, decreasing the outlet TI levels so that the flow is more uniform and this influence is more significant as the mass flow rate increases.

Figure 22 Outlet profiles for configuration Aluminium 1, 4, 5, and 6 at 10g/s

Finally, a comparison of the outlet velocity and TI profiles for different configurations of Aluminium single elements, measured with an inlet flow rate of 10g/s, is proposed in Figure 22. The mean velocity profile is strongly affected by the internal fin geometries. Configurations 1 and 6 are strongly packed and behave similarly, as a porous material, providing a flat profile at the channel center. The velocity profile of both configurations 4 reflects the M shape of the fins, as shown in Table 8. The difference in fin thicknesses influences the boundary layer thickness, being higher with larger fins. Finally, the configuration 5 is also reflected in the mean velocity profile, showing one major peak at the channel center followed by two side peaks, corresponding to the center X and the bottom and top half X shapes.

Table 8 Internal geometries for Aluminium configurations 1, 4, 5, and 6

In terms of TI, the configurations 1 and 6, with a lower porosity, are experiencing a flat TI at the channel center while the configurations 4 and 5, with a lower porosity, are showing stronger fluctuations of the TI at the channel center.

As a further processing, the average TI in the channel center was compared for the different configurations, together with the measured pressure drop for that flow rate, in Figure 23. There is a general trend showing that as the pressure drop increases, turbulence intensity decreases, similarly to a porous material. However, turbulence level is higher for the gyroid compared to the reference offset-strip fins (6 vs. 1) as the latter shows lower pressure drop.

Figure 23 Mean TI vs. Pressure drop for 10g/s

4. Thermal measurements

This section focuses on the thermal characterization of all the samples listed in the table 5. When passing through the heated sample, the airflow undergoes a change of temperature due to the heat addition. As much heat as possible has to be transferred into the fluid while passing into the module, and so the heat exchange between the air and the solid surface has to be efficient. To enhance this heat exchange, the heat losses to the ambient were also minimized as much as possible by the mean of external insulation of the sample, except for the bottom surface. As explained in 2.2., thermocouples were exploited for the temperature measurements of the fluid flowing in the sample and at the outlet and inlet sections. Moreover, the IR thermography was used to acquire the data concerning the temperature distribution along the bottom wall of the channels. The heat transfer coefficient, which is the parameter of interest for the comparison of the different samples, was retrieved from the inlet and outlet temperatures measurement. This coefficient is also adimensionnalized for further comparison of the samples.

4.1. Temperature evolutions

4.1.1. Outlet temperature profiles

The outlet thermocouples rake consists of nine thermocouples located along a cross: there are five thermocouples horizontally and five vertically as shown in Figure 4. The results obtained are differing a bit for each one of the materials considered, as, in this case, the temperature detected by the thermocouples depends on the thermal conductivity of both materials of the CHX modules, but also on the shape of the fin geometry, which are conducting differently the heat. The analysis has been led on the temperature distribution vertical and horizontal and the results compared for each material and for every geometry.

The acquisition of the temperature was at 10 Hz for 20 s. This frequency has been chosen low since the acquisition was conducted once the temperature variation observed for each thermocouple was stationary. The measurements were carried on for a mass flow range from 3 g/s to 20 g/s for the Aluminum samples, and for a range from 10 g/s to 20 g/s for the Inconel samples, and a Joule power equal to 130W for both the materials. Because of the low dissipative capacity of heat of Inconel, the temperature under the resistance for low air mass-flow reached values that were quite close to the maximum temperature acceptable by the electrical resistance. In order to avoid the risk of damaging the electrical resistance, it was decided not to test air mass-flows below 10 g/s for the last samples made in Inconel tested.

The temperature detected with the probes of the outlet rake is expected to mirror the temperature distribution along the fins at the outlet section. Hence, the gradient should be higher in the vertical direction and more evident for the Inconel channel than the Aluminum, due to its higher thermal resistivity. The profiles obtained confirm the previsions.

Figure 24 shows the results for the horizontal profiles obtained for both materials and for every CHX modules, for four different mass flow rates.

a) Aluminum sample 5g/s

b) Aluminum sample 10g/s

c) Inconel sample 10g/s

d) Aluminum sample 15g/s

e) Inconel sample 15g/s

f) Aluminum sample 20g/s

g) Inconel sample 20g/s

Figure 24: Horizontal outlet temperature profile

The profiles for the Aluminum show, for half of the geometries (V1, V41, V9 and V10), a uniform temperature distribution (Fig. 24). For those geometries, the maximum variation in temperature is around 0.5 °C and a small increase is detected on the right side of the rake for V1 and V9 for instance.

The results for the Inconel are a bit different (Fig. 24). There is an effective temperature gradient in the horizontal direction for all the mass flow rates and for all the geometries, except for N9 and N10, even if it is higher as the flow velocity decreases. The highest temperature value is obtained in correspondence of the middle of the section, but a small increase is also present on the right side of the rake for almost every geometry. Obviously, the

physical behavior of the phenomena is the same, but, due to the low thermal conductivity of the Inconel, the temperature gradients are more evident for this material (up to 3°C for N9).

A physical explanation for these trends stands in the considerations about the heat exchange mechanisms: the highest temperature is detected in correspondence of the middle of the section because this is the region which is less influenced by 'border effects', such as losses through the ambient, which are always slowly present nevertheless the insulation and dissipation due to the conductivity through the fins and the CHX case, depending on the properties of the material. These are the main reasons why the gradients are more evident for the Inconel 718.

However, since some variations are also noticeable for half of the aluminum samples and on the contrary the Inconel samples N9 and N10 do not present variation in their horizontal outlet temperature profiles, the reason cannot be narrowed down only to the material. Thereby, a piece of explanation could also come from the fin arrangement itself inside the samples and from the size of the outlet cross-section which is smaller for the geometries 9 and 10 for both materials. The section being smaller, by consequence the length of the fin is smaller, and so this makes the geometries more sensitive to "border effects" to the bottom than the other geometries, especially for the Inconel. Thence, more heat can be evacuated by the bottom and the outlet profile is flattened compared to samples with higher fins height.

Another important observation can be done on a possible reason which generates the small increase of the temperature measured by the thermocouple on the right side of the rake. To get a justification, the IR thermography has been used to observe the temperature distribution at the outlet section of the CHX module (Fig. 25).

Figure 25: Qualitative image obtained with the IR camera of the outlet temperature distribution.

The images have been obtained in the same operating conditions for both the materials ($Q_{\text{Joule}} = 130\text{W}$ and $m = 3\text{ g/s}$). The right side is always hotter than the left one and this is due to the fact that on this side there is the junction of the resistance which is not glue on the sample

but, having the welding of the two electric cables of the electric supply, is always at higher temperature. The lateral right wall is influenced by this effect, which is always more visible for the Inconel (circled area in Fig. 25b) than for the Aluminum, as, because of the higher thermal resistivity, the heat dissipation is not uniform. This effect of non-uniformity is not really appreciable of the Aluminum.

Considering all the comments done until now, the vertical temperature profile is easy to predict. The temperature gradient appears increasing from the bottom to the top of the section and this gradient is much more evident for the Inconel CHX element (Fig. 26). This is mirroring the negative temperature gradient along the fins from the upper part (this is the area closest to the heating plate) to the bottom. This is due to both the cooling effect of the flow blowing inside the channel and the conductive resistance of the fins, depending on the material. This gradient, however, is less evident for lower mass flow rates and for the Aluminum as, thanks to its high thermal conductivity, the fins are characterized by higher thermal efficiency, hence a lower temperature variation along them. The maximum temperature difference for the Aluminum is equal to 2.7 °C (Fig. 26a), while for the Inconel is around 32.2 °C (Fig. 26b).

(a) Aluminium 10g/s.

(b) Inconel 718 10g/s

Figure 26: Vertical outlet temperature profile

4.1.2. Temperature evolution inside the channel

A temperature variation of the flow stream flowing in the CHX module can be obtained only if there is a heat source of the fluid. In this set-up, an electric heating resistance is glued on the top wall of the sample, providing heat flux by Joule effect. It is important to ensure that the heat flux is uniform to have the same amount of heat transferred along the sample to the internal blowing flow.

Heat flux is defined as a flow of thermal energy per unit of area and time. For solids, heat is mainly transported by conduction and the heat flux is described by Fourier's law:

$$\dot{q} = -k \frac{dT(x)}{dx}$$

where k is the thermal conductivity of the material and the minus expresses the flowing of the heat power to negative gradient temperature areas. The equation of Fourier above shows that uniform heat flux means a linear rise of the fluid temperature flowing in the duct as function of the distance x from the entrance (Fig. 27) [3].

Figure 27: Uniform heat flux

The results obtained for both the samples show quite a good agreement with this theory as the trend of the temperature read by the thermocouples installed under the electric resistance is rather linear and the same trend is also retrieved by the probes located in the flow stream between the fins.

a) Aluminum sample 5g/s

b) Aluminum sample 10g/s

c) Inconel sample 10g/s

d) Aluminum sample 15g/s

e) Inconel sample 15g/s

f) Aluminum sample 20g/s

g) Inconel sample 20g/s

Figure 28: Temperature measured under the resistance for every sample and air mass-flow

Figure 28 shows the trend of the temperature detected with the five thermocouples located under the heating plate for five reference mass flow rates. Several conclusions can be drawn from these graphs.

The first one is that every geometry for both materials presents an almost linear increasing trend across the sample. For two geometries (1/1b and 6), and for both Aluminum and Inconel, the trend is even more fitting to the theory, since the trend is very linear, except for a small declining trend between the last two points. However, the first thermocouple for the sample N6 measures a very high temperature value. Since this value is declining from 102 °C at 10 g/s to around 90°C at 20 g/s, it would not be illogical to assume a defect of the thermocouple itself.

All the other geometries show a saw-tooth trend due to the fact that the third thermocouple located at the middle of the sample, measures a slightly lower temperature. This profile could come from the fact that the electrical resistance thanks to electrical wires welded on a frame. Thus, the heating might not be fully uniform. Thereby, the point 3 could be located between two electrical wires whereas the point 2 and 4 could be closer from a heating zone, which would lead to a lower value read by the third thermocouple. For each given geometry, the temperature profile under the resistance is quite equivalent for both materials. This is especially quite striking for the samples V5 and N5 and for every mass-flow. Indeed, their curves show very similar trends.

This can lead to the conclusion that, even if the effect of the material is not inexistent at all, the main reason for the shape of the curve arises from the inlet fin arrangement of the modules. The effect of the material on the trend can be firstly seen in the overall temperature gradient across the sample, between the thermocouple 1 and 5 under the resistance. As a matter of fact, this gradient is higher for Inconel than for Aluminum due to its low dissipation capacity. For instance for the geometry 5 and at 15 g/s, it is worth a bit less than 30°C for Aluminum across the CHX module and 40°C for Inconel. The second effect of the material on the shape of the curve can be noticed through the amplitude of the saw-tooth trend, and thus through the values of the temperature gradients between the thermocouples 2 and 3, and between 3 and 4. The point 3 located at the middle of the sample tends to have an even lower value when compared to the thermocouple 2 and 4 for the Inconel samples, than for the Aluminum. Thence, the temperature gradients at this location are more important in the case of the Inconel CHX modules, leading to a more pronounced saw-tooth shape of the curve due to its thermal resistivity.

Another parameter also has an important impact on the amplitude of these saw-tooth shaped curves. Indeed, as the mass flow increases, it can be noticed that for both material, the value of the thermocouple 3 show an even higher difference with the thermocouple 2 and 4. This is especially noticeable for Aluminum. Indeed, at 5g/s, the trend of the temperature under the resistance is almost fully linear, whereas from 10 g/s and for higher mass-flow, the thermocouple 3 shows a lower value than the two surrounding ones.

It can be also noticed that the last thermocouple is measuring a slightly lower temperature for some geometries and especially for the Inconel samples, creating a declining trend of the curve. This is due to its location, as it is placed at the end of the heating plate the probes installed at the extremities of the heating plate are more affected by the influence of the low temperature of the limiting areas which are not heated, and by the surrounding air at ambient temperature.

Figure 29: Mean temperature under the resistance as a function of the air mass-flow

Another important effect generated by the high resistivity of the Inconel is the absolute value of the temperature under the resistance and inside the flow compared with the one of the Aluminum. In particular, for the same heating power (130W) and mass flow, the temperature measured under the heating plate in the Inconel channel is up to the double of the one obtained for the Aluminum in each point (Fig 29). This is effectively due to the high resistance of the upper wall of the sample to the heat flux in the vertical direction and as a consequence, the temperatures values of the inner flow are quite similar for both materials (Fig. 30 and Fig. 31). This phenomenon can help to predict, for the same heating power, a lower forced convection heat transfer coefficient for the Inconel channel as it is inversely proportional to the temperature difference between the temperature of the wall and the one of the flow.

a) Aluminum sample

b) Inconel sample

Figure 30: Mean fluid temperature inside the channel

A last consideration can be done about the effect of the mass flow on the temperature distribution. Indeed, the mass flow is mainly affecting the amplitude of the temperature trend and less its shape, but the absolute temperature values are decreased as the mass flow increases; the reason stands in the fact that the growth of the air blown in the channel means an enhancement of the cooling of the sample walls, as the efficiency of the heat transfer is enhancing with the flow velocity.

a) Aluminum sample 5g/s

b) Aluminum sample 10g/s

c) Inconel sample 10g/s

d) Aluminum sample 15g/s

e) Inconel sample 15g/s

f) Aluminum sample 20g/s

g) Inconel sample 20g/s

Figure 31: Trend of the temperatures measured by the five thermocouples located inside the channels

The thermocouples located inside the channels (Fig. 31) show a different trend from the ones under the resistance (Fig. 28) even though those ten thermocouples are facing each other, since they are located at the same distance from the inlet one to another. Indeed, apart from

two thermocouples, being the first thermocouple of V9 and the second one of N10 that seems to have a defect since their temperature measured is barely changing between the tests, all the other measurements of temperature show a linear trend along the samples that is in good agreement with the theory (Fig. 31).

As explained above, the temperature of the inner flow is quite similar for both Inconel and Aluminum (Fig 30). Thereby, the conclusion deriving from this tends to state that the mean outlet temperature would be also similar for both materials. Since the inlet temperature is almost constant for every measurement carried, the inlet-outlet temperature difference, which is the driving parameter of the heat exchange assessment, would then also show similar trends and values. This is confirmed on the Figure 32 showing the overall temperature difference between the inlet and the outlet of the sample for Aluminum and Inconel. Indeed, the values of this temperature difference range from 30-35°C at 3g/s, to 7-13°C at 10 g/s and around 4-5°C at 20g/s. In addition, the curves for Aluminum samples and the curves for Inconel samples show very similar trend.

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 32: Inlet-outlet temperature difference

It is recalled that heat is brought to the CHX module by an electrical resistance glued on its upper surface, which is set to transfer 130W to its surrounding. In order to limit the heat losses to the ambient, and to force the heat to be transferred into the air all the samples are covered by a layer of insulation Fiberfrax except at their bottom surfaces, to enable the IR measurements. However, the heat losses cannot be neglected, meaning that the heat gained by the fluid is not exactly equal to the heat provided by the resistance. The heat gained by the air while passing through the sample is calculated from the elevation of temperature measured by the inlet and outlet thermocouple rakes (Fig 32) as follows:

$$\dot{Q}_{air} = \dot{m}C_p(T_{air,out} - T_{air,in})$$

It is important to assess that the heat gained by the air is not far from the value of the heat added by the electrical resistance, meaning that the losses are negligible. Figure 33 show the ratio of heat transferred to the fluid over the total heat added to the system. The first noticeable fact is that the amount of heat captured by the air is decreasing as the mass-flow is increasing, and so that the heat losses have an increasing importance. Part of the explanation can come from the fact that as more air is flowing into the sample, more heat is exchanged between the fluid and the solid. Thus, more heat is passing to the solid structure and that conducts it to the bottom of the sample as well as the inlet-outlet flanges, creating heat losses.

This declining trend is even more pronounced for Inconel. At 20 g/s, the heat losses represent at least 30% of the initial heat provided by the electrical resistance, whereas it represents around 15-20% for most of the Aluminum sample at the same mass-flow.

This is due to its high thermal resistivity: because the heat is not so efficiently conducted through the outer sample solid and the fins and so not so efficiently transferred to the fluid, and that it still has to be evacuated somehow, the heat is then lost through the inlet and outlet flanges and rakes by conduction. The heat is conducted more easily within the whole sample for the Aluminum and thus more transferred into the fluid, which leads to a limitation of the heat losses to the surrounding.

Another effect on the declining trend could come from the electrical generator supplying the resistance that creates the heat by Joule effect. Indeed, it was noticed during the last test that the power supplied by the generator to the resistance by slowly declining during the tests, up to 10% of the initial value of 130W, and especially for the measurements on the Inconel samples. This is due to the fact that those tests were taking more time since to reach again the steady-state of the system after changing the air mass flow, required to wait a while more than for Aluminum, due to the thermal inertia of the Inconel samples.

a) Aluminum CHX module

b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 33: Ratio of the heat added to the system and the heat transferred into the fluid

4.1.3. Bottom wall temperatures

The temperature distribution along the bottom surface of the CHX channel has been retrieved exploiting the IR thermography. Firstly, the IR camera was calibrated using as reference a thermocouple type K. The measurements have been executed keeping the IR camera at the

same distance from the sample used during the calibration. The acquisition was performed once the temperature trend was observed to be stationary along the sample. The frequency of acquisition was 10 Hz and a duration of 20 s, for a total of 200 frames for each measurement. The data have been recorded for mass flow rates varying from 3 g/s to 20 g/s and a Joule power of 130W for both the materials.

Figure 34: Temperature contours of the geometry 1 samples at 5g/s

Figure 34 shows an example of the temperature contours obtained for $m = 5 \text{ g/s}$ for the geometry 1 for both Aluminum and Inconel. The main temperature gradient is present in the longitudinal direction; the transversal one can be considered negligible thanks to the presence of the insulation on the lateral sides of the sample. It can be observed that the temperature distribution along the channel is increasing linearly along the Aluminum channel, with a temperature gradient which is higher than the one obtained with the Inconel for the same operating conditions. This difference becomes even higher as the mass flow increases, as the gradient of temperature for the Inconel is decreasing, while for the Aluminum it is still important (Fig. 35).

Figure 35 shows the longitudinal temperature profiles along the channel wall for all the samples and for every mass-flow. For the same operating conditions, the profiles of the Aluminum always show high temperature levels. The temperature profile increases on a linear trend to stabilize around a constant value at the end of the channel. For the Inconel, the trend is also linear, but both the absolute values of temperature and the temperature gradient along the surface are lower. It is interesting to comment the small decrease of temperature at the beginning of the channel that present some geometries like V5 and V6, followed by an inversion of trend. This behavior is due to the cooling effect of the inlet fresh air combined with the heat power produced by the heating plate; this generates an inflection point in the temperature trend which is more pronounced for the Inconel because of its higher resistance to the heat transfer. Some bumps and oscillations can be noticed on the profiles of the samples N2, N3 and N6. The most plausible explanation lies in the fact that the black painting covering the bottom surface of the sample might be non-uniform.

Figure 35: Longitudinal temperature profile for every sample

Concerning the cases of $m= 15 \text{ g/s}$ and $m= 20 \text{ g/s}$, it can be observed that the Aluminum still presents gradients of up to 7°C and 4°C respectively, while for the Inconel the gradient is around 2°C for $m= 15 \text{ g/s}$ and it is not even significant for higher mass flow, as the variation of temperature is within the uncertainty bounds of the IR camera, corresponding to $\pm 1.2^\circ\text{C}$, in a confidence interval of 95%. This value of uncertainty is discussed and retrieved in §A.

4.2. Heat transfer coefficient

The most important form of heat exchange in the module takes place by forced convection. The temperatures measured by the mean of thermocouples aim at calculating the heat balance in the CHX module, and at retrieving the heat transfer coefficient, specific at each

sample. This parameter is not easy to retrieve as it depends on several aspects: fluid properties, surface geometry and flow conditions.

4.2.1. Heat transfer coefficient definitions

As the experiments performed in the framework of this study have strong similarities with the work of Stimpson et al. 2016 [6] on coupons, it was decided to define in a similar way the convective heat transfer coefficient:

$$h_{conv} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{air}}{A_{exch} \Delta T_{LM}}$$

Where Q_{air} is the heat gained by the air in the sample, A_{exch} is the heat exchange area, and ΔT_{LM} is the log mean temperature difference defined as [4]:

$$\Delta T_{LM} = \frac{T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}}{\ln\left(\frac{T_t - T_{air,in}}{T_t - T_{air,out}}\right)}$$

As mentioned above, the temperatures of the incoming and outgoing airflow are obtained from the thermocouples associated to the inlet and outlet rakes. The wall temperature T_t is obtained from the mean value of the temperatures measured by the five thermocouples located between the resistance and the sample upper wall [8]:

$$T_t = T_s - \frac{\dot{Q}_{joule}}{A_{res}} \left(\frac{t_{wall}}{k_m} \right)$$

Where Q_{joule} is the heat provided by the electrical resistance, A_{res} is the surface area of the resistance and is worth 5000mm², t_{wall} is the thickness of wall through which conduction occurs and is worth 0.5mm, and k_m is the thermal conductivity of the material (170 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ for Aluminum and 10.5 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ for Inconel 718).

Indeed, this definition takes into account the heat losses, the actual surface area that is used during the heat transfer process. However, it implies a homogenous and symmetrical profile of the wall temperature which is not entirely correct, especially for Inconel. For each configuration, the wetted surface areas are listed on table 9.

	V1	V4 ₁	V4 ₂	V5	V6	V7	V9	V10
A_{exch} (10⁻²m²)	7.26	5.94	5.96	6.32	13.0	4.63	6.48	4.22

(a) Aluminum samples heat exchange areas

	N1	N1b	N2	N3	N5	N6	N7	N9	N10
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$A_{\text{exch}} (10^{-2} \text{m}^2)$	7.26	7.26	5.86	5.86	6.32	13.0	4.63	5.36	4.74
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(b) Inconel samples heat exchange areas

Table 9: Heat exchange areas of all the configurations

The configurations presenting the most important areas for heat exchange are the geometries 1 and 6, and on the other hand, the ones presenting the smallest wetted surface area are the geometries 7 and 10.

4.2.2. Comparison of configurations

As explained in section 3.1.2, nine configurations of Inconel samples and eight configurations of Aluminum samples were tested. For each configuration, the convective heat transfer was retrieved by the method detailed in the previous section, and all the values are presented on the Figure 36, as long as the Nusselt number that compares the convective to the conductive heat transfer:

$$Nu = \frac{h_{\text{conv}} \cdot D_h}{k_{\text{air}}}$$

(a) Aluminum samples

It appears from the Figure 36 that the order of geometries in terms of heat area exchange, from the greatest to the smallest (Table 9) is not identical to the one in terms of convective heat coefficient. This means that the heat exchange area alone is not the parameter driving the amount of heat transferred from the solid to the fluid. Indeed, the geometries V1/N1/N1b

and V9 presented an important amount of surface for the heat transfer compared to the other geometries, and they also show a high convective heat coefficient. However, the geometries V7/N7, N9 and V10/N10 that have the two smallest heat exchange areas, present an also high convective heat coefficient. Besides, those five geometries, along with V9, have the same particularity: they have a smaller outlet cross-section area than the other geometries (up to 60% less). As the fluid passage area decreases, the fluid accelerates which enhances the convective heat transfer between the solid (walls and fins) and the air. The highest is the velocity of the fluid; the better will be the convective heat exchange.

(b) Inconel samples

Figure 36: Convective heat transfer coefficients and Nusselt numbers for every sample

Thus, it is consistent that the geometry V9 which has the smallest fluid passage area and a great heat transfer surface, present the highest convective heat coefficient. For the geometry N9, the fluid passage area is also very small when compared to the others, but its very high convective heat transfer coefficient comes from its higher fin density. For the geometries V7/N7 and V10/N10, although they do not have a high A_{exch} , thanks to their smaller fluid passage area, they also present a high convective heat coefficient.

Within the geometries of constant section, the geometries V4₁, V4₂, N2 and N3 obtain quite good convective performances, given their medium value of heat transfer area. The difference between the two curves for Aluminum derives from the slightly higher heat exchange area of

V4₂ than V4₁. The geometries V6/N6 shows poor convective results given their high heat exchange area, and a downward trend for the Aluminum sample. This could come from their geometrical features. Indeed, due to the wavy shape of the fins, there is a possibility that the outlet temperature is not stabilized enough at the outlet section, and that the temperature measured by the outlet rake is not representative of the actual mean value, leading to its poor convective results. Finally, the geometries V5/N5 also presents quite poor convective heat transfer results considered their heat transfer area. This is mainly due to the fact that this geometry has continuous channels unlike the other geometries, and so the thermal boundary layer is never broken [10] [11]. On the contrary it expands along the walls of the channels through the sample, which inhibits an efficient heat exchange. This is also the reason why as the Reynolds increases, the convective heat transfer coefficient increases a lot. Indeed, the effects of an increase of mass flow has more influence on this geometry than on the others, since the enhancement of the turbulence that arises from an increase of Reynolds number, enhances a lot the convection, whereas in the other geometries the turbulence within the samples is already quite high due to their shapes [9].

The Nusselt numbers for all the geometries are interesting to plot, since besides the information about the convective heat coefficient, it also takes into account the hydraulic diameter, and so some information about the friction, since the pressure losses are partly related to the hydraulic diameter. For the geometries V1/N1/N1b and V10/N10, their position curve to one another does not change since their hydraulic diameter is of the same order.

However, for the geometry V6/N6, V7/N7 and V9/N9, since their hydraulic diameters are smaller, their performances in terms of Nusselt are lowered, while on the other hand the performances of the samples N2, N3, N41 and N42 are enhanced due to their great value of hydraulic diameters.

4.2.3. Non-dimensional analysis: Colburn and goodness factors

The convective heat transfer coefficient is usually adimensionnalized for compact heat exchangers [5] through the Colburn factor which is equivalent to the Fanning factor but for heat transfer and is expressed as follows:

$$j = St \cdot Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{Nu \cdot Pr^{-\frac{1}{3}}}{Re}$$

Where St and Pr stands for the dimensionless numbers Stanton and Prandtl. Since the same fluid at the same state is used for all the measurements, the Prandtl number is equivalent for all the samples. Thus, comparing the Colburn number is equivalent in the present study at comparing the Stanton numbers obtained from all the measurements. The Stanton number evaluates the ratio between the heat transfer into the fluid and the thermal capacity of the fluid and is defined as follows:

$$St = \frac{Nu}{Re Pr}$$

Thereby, the higher the Stanton number of a sample and in the present case also the Colburn number, the best was the heat exchange, so the best are the thermal performances of this sample.

(a) Aluminum samples

(b) Inconel samples

Figure 37: Colburn factor for every sample

The same main conclusion in terms Colburn factor can be drawn for both materials (Fig. 37). Indeed, the geometry 9 presents in both cases the best thermal performance and the geometries 5 and 6 the lowest ones, with a rather important difference with all the samples. Concerning the standard design (Geometry 1), it is interesting to notice that the Aluminum version reaches a quite high heat performance, whereas for its Inconel version, the samples N2, N3 and N10 obtained better thermal results. It is also relevant to notice that as one could predict, the Aluminum samples obtained, generally speaking, higher Colburn factors that the Inconel samples.

Another important dimensionless parameter is the volume goodness factor (VGF) expressed as follows:

$$\text{Volume goodness factor} = \frac{j}{f^{1/3}}$$

Its aims at comparing two factors giving only partial indication of the performances of the CHX module, i.e. the heat transfer through the Colburn factor and the pressure losses through the Fanning factor, in order to obtain a more complete indicator. Indeed, since the final objective is to obtain a Compact Heat Exchanger exchanging the maximum heat possible with the lowest penalty on the pressure drops, the comparison between the two contributions has to be

reliable. A high volume goodness factor means a more performant geometry in terms of compromise between the heat exchange and the pressure drops [7].

(a) Aluminum samples

The trend of the volume good factor is generally decreasing as the Reynold increases for all the samples (Fig. 38), meaning that the enhancement of the heat exchange due to the rise of the velocity does not compensate sufficiently the higher friction losses that come at higher velocity. Several considerations can be done on these plots. The first one is that the order in the geometries from the most performant to the less one is very different between Inconel and Aluminum. The only common feature lies in the geometry 6 that has the lowest performance for both materials. The sample V10 achieves the best overall results for the Aluminum, whereas the sample N9 does in the case of Inconel. As a reminder, it was stated previously (Fig. 12) that the samples V5 and N5 generates the same amount of very low friction losses. Thereby, given the thermal properties of Aluminum, the sample V5 is obviously showing high overall performances. Given their good heat exchange area, their high hydraulic diameter and their low surface roughness's, the Inconel CHX modules N2 and N3, as well as the Aluminum CHX modules V4₁ and V4₂ obtained great and very similar volume goodness factors. Last but not least, it is important to notice that the order of magnitude of the volume goodness factors of the Inconel and Aluminum samples are equivalent. It means that the good thermal capacity of the Aluminum material is balanced by the better surface finish of the Inconel samples.

(b) Inconel samples

Figure 38: Volume goodness factors of every sample

5. Conclusions

The objective of this first report was to summarize the work of T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 from WP4 of NATHENA project. These tasks are all related to the aerothermal experimental characterization of single elements with varying geometries.

The task T4.1 had the objective of designing and building the experimental facility. The facility consists in a compressed air supply with regulating valve and flow meter, followed by a rectangular channel with the same dimensions as the 1st elementary channel. The channel is then fixed to the facility with a flange, and heat flux is applied on the top of the sample through the use of a thermal resistance. The channel is insulated on his top and side walls. The top wall is left uninsulated to allow IR measurements of the heat losses through the bottom wall.

The task T4.2 had the objective of designing and characterizing the instrumentation. The aeraulic characterization consisted in the measurement of the volumetric flow rate upstream the channel, the measurement of the static pressure along the sample using a row of 5 pressure taps, and the measurement of vertical velocity profiles at the inlet and the outlet of the channel for some of the geometries. The thermal characterization consisted in the measurement of the inlet (4 thermocouples) and outlet temperatures (2 profiles: 1 horizontal and 1 vertical with 9 thermocouples in total), the temperature along the sample in the fluid, on top of the sample below the resistance, and on the external bottom wall using the IR camera. All measurement techniques were calibrated and the uncertainty analysis is present in appendix as well as some key values in the report.

Finally, the task 4.3 had the objective of measuring the different channels. Originally 20 single element modules were planned to test the surface finish, the effect of texture design, the influence of the fin design, the channel design, and the effect of cross-section variation. However, some modules experienced problems during the manufacturing. Therefore, 17 samples were finally tested; 8 in Aluminium and 9 in Inconel.

In terms of pressure drop, the analysis focused on the linear pressure drop inside the fin arrangement, leaving out inlet and outlet effects (as some geometries have a strong restriction before the fin arrangement). The pressure drop inside the fin arrangement is linear for most of the geometries. The main conclusions are that Aluminum CHX geometries generally show higher total pressure drops than Inconel (except for geometries 9 and 10) as the roughness is higher for Aluminium samples. The evolution of pressure drop with flow rate is linked both to the roughness of the sample, but also to the internal fin arrangement and the sample height. Indeed, all geometries show their linear pressure drop for a similar flow rate decreasing with the porosity and the hydraulic diameter, but not showing a perfect alignment of all samples. The roughness shows an effect as well when similar geometries with different roughness are compared (like N1 and N1b, and N2 and N3). Finally, the analysis of the Fanning factor shows

a linear decrease with Re in the laminar regime even though all curves are not always fitting each other due to roughness influence. The Fanning factor is then reaching a minimum and increases again when starting the transition regime up to a plateau which is not always visible due to the mass flow range used in this study, which is too small. However, the plateau was estimated and used to fit an equivalent roughness from the Colebrook method. This equivalent roughness increases linearly with the measured roughness, similarly to other samples from additive manufacturing measured in literature.

The thermal analysis focused first in the analysis of the outlet temperature profiles, the temperature profile in the fluid and under the resistance, the temperature profile at the external bottom wall.

The outlet horizontal profiles show mostly a uniform temperature, showing in some samples, and mostly for Inconel samples, a higher temperature at the center of the channel, which can be explained as this region is less influenced by border effects such as losses through the ambient due to the conductivity through the fins and the CHX case. The outlet vertical profiles were plotted for samples with the same fin height (up to geometry 6), and show similar evolution with the top surface at higher temperature than the bottom, as the heat flux is provided through the top wall. The temperature gradient within the sample is a lot higher for Inconel 718, due to its lower conductivity.

The evolution of the temperature below the resistance show mostly a linear evolution, indication that the heat flux applied is uniform. However, some geometries show a saw-tooth trend due to the fact that the third thermocouple located at the middle of the sample, measures a slightly lower temperature. This effect can partly be explained by a position of thermocouple in between two electrical wire of the resistance. But the material plays a role as this effect is more pronounced with Inconel due to its low dissipation capacity. Finally, thermal losses through the channel exit can be visible for some geometries, especially in Inconel, indicating a stronger influence of this measurement point with the limiting areas which are not heated. The evolution of temperature in the fluid is linear for all geometries and both materials. The gradient increases with Aluminium compared to Inconel.

The heat gained by the air in the sample is compared to the applied heat from the thermal resistance. Most samples show a more or less good correspondence at low mass flow rate, but the amount of heat captured by the air is decreasing as the mass-flow is increasing, and illustrated that the heat losses have an increasing importance. Part of the explanation can come from the fact that as more air is flowing into the sample, more heat is exchanged between the fluid and the solid. Thus, more heat is passing to the solid structure and that

conducts it to the bottom of the sample as well as the inlet-outlet flanges, creating heat losses. This declining trend is even more pronounced for Inconel, due to its high thermal resistivity.

To take into account the effect of the fin design as well as the effective heat flux gained by the air, a definition of the heat transfer coefficient using the Q_{air} , a logarithmic temperature difference using the temperature at the top of the sample but also the inlet and outlet temperatures, and the total exchange area available in the sample is used. The results are presented in terms of Nusselt number. The Reynolds is calculated using the hydraulic diameter of the sample. The order of geometries in terms of heat area exchange, from the greatest to the smallest is not identical to the one in terms of convective heat coefficient, indicating the heat exchange area alone is not sufficient to explain the thermal efficiency of the samples. But it shows also that the geometries with a smaller outlet cross-section area have higher heat transfer coefficient. As the fluid passage area decreases, for a similar mass flow rate, the fluid accelerates which enhances the convective heat transfer between the solid (walls and fins) and the air. The highest is the velocity of the fluid; the better will be the convective heat exchange. The results were also presented in terms of Colburn factor. With both materials, the geometry 9 presents the best thermal performance and the geometries 5 and 6 the lowest ones, with a rather important difference with all the samples. Concerning the standard design (Geometry 1), it is interesting to notice that the Aluminum version reaches a quite high heat performance, whereas for its Inconel version, the samples N2, N3 and N10 obtained better thermal results. It is also relevant to notice that as one could predict, the Aluminum samples obtained, generally speaking, higher Colburn factors than the Inconel samples.

Finally, both aerodynamic and thermal performances are compared using the goodness factor, which is the ratio between the Colburn factor and the Fanning factor (to the power 1/3). Indeed, since the final objective is to obtain a Compact Heat Exchanger exchanging the maximum heat possible with the lowest penalty on the pressure drops, the comparison between the two contributions has to be reliable. A high volume goodness factor means a more performant geometry in terms of compromise between the heat exchange and the pressure drops. The trend of the volume good factor is generally decreasing as the Reynolds increases for all the samples, meaning that the enhancement of the heat exchange due to the rise of the velocity does not compensate sufficiently the higher friction losses that come at higher velocity. The comparison of geometries shows that the order in the geometries from the most performant to the less one is very different between Inconel and Aluminum. The sample V10 achieves the best overall results for the Aluminum, whereas the sample N9 does in the case of Inconel. As a reminder, it was stated previously that the samples V5 and N5 generates the same amount of very low friction losses. Thereby, given the thermal properties of Aluminum, the sample V5 is obviously showing high overall performances. Given their good heat exchange area, their high hydraulic diameter and their low surface roughness's, the Inconel CHX modules N2 and N3, as well as the Aluminum CHX modules V4₁ and V4₂ obtained

great and very similar volume goodness factors. Last but not least, it is important to notice that the order of magnitude of the volume goodness factors of the Inconel and Aluminum samples are equivalent. It means that the good thermal capacity of the Aluminum material is balanced by the better surface finish of the Inconel samples.

In conclusions, the experimental characterization for the single channel elements shows that the chosen geometries for the elementary cross flow channel are among the best in terms of aerothermal performances. Another important conclusion from the measurement is that the roughness, different between the samples, influenced the results so that a proper comparison of the geometries was not always possible.

It is important to also draw conclusions about the measurements and the analysis. This study showed that the definition of the heat transfer coefficient, but also the proper measurement of the outlet temperature can strongly influence the conclusions. However, a majority of the issues encountered in this phase were related to the use of a thermal resistance and the presence of a bottom wall with thermal losses. This will not be present in the cross-flow elementary channels where the heat exchange will come from the fluid themselves, but also the whole channel will be insulated. But it will be important to focus on a proper measurement of the outlet temperature, maybe with the addition of a mixing chamber downstream the hot and cold outlets. Finally, a literature study will be made on the different possibilities to determine the heat transfer coefficient in a cross-flow heat exchanger.

6. Appendix A

Uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty expresses the lack of accurate knowledge about the values of a measured property. Error and uncertainty can come from several reasons: the measuring instruments, the item to be measured, the measurement process, the propagation of uncertainty of other measurements, the environment, the operator skills. In case a property is deduced as a function of different measured quantities, the uncertainty is obtained on the basis of the law of error propagation: the determination of an output quantity error on the basis of known errors of input quantities is obtained using the expansion of the model function in a Taylor series up to the first-order terms. The error associated with an indirect measurement is commonly deduced as a mean square error:

$$\Delta y = \sqrt{\left(\Delta x_1 \frac{\partial y}{\partial x_1}\right)^2 + \left(\Delta x_2 \frac{\partial y}{\partial x_2}\right)^2 + \dots + \left(\Delta x_n \frac{\partial y}{\partial x_n}\right)^2}$$

where the partial derivative $\frac{\partial y}{\partial x_i}$, calculated at the points x_i is called sensitivity index to the input x_i , the variable y is function of [13]. To calculate the uncertainty it is important to first individualize all the possible sources related to it. There are two main kinds of uncertainties:

- Type A: estimated using statistics, when a series of n measurements is taken. The estimated standard uncertainty is defined as:

$$\Delta = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$$

where σ is the standard deviation.

- Type B: estimated from any other information, such as calibration certificates, calculations, published information, common sense. In this case the estimation of the uncertainty is more difficult and only the upper and lower limits are predictable, so the measured value can likely fall in between. A rectangular distribution is usually used:

$$\Delta = \frac{a}{\sqrt{3}}$$

where a is the semi-range between the two boundary limits [14]. These different kinds of standard uncertainties can be combined by root sum of the square and the result is known as combined standard uncertainty:

$$\Delta_{combined} = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + \dots}$$

The uncertainty values are usually re-scaled multiplying them for a coverage factor K, which gives a particular confidence interval. Usually a coverage factor equal to 2 is chosen, as it gives a level of confidence interval of 95%.

In the following sections the uncertainty calculation procedures on the main measurements led during the project are illustrated.

6.1. Pressure drop measurements

The pressure drop measurements have been performed using a pressure transducer, measuring the pressure drop between two pressure taps. The transducer, with membranes of a maximum pressure ranging from 0.3 psi to 3.0 psi (Table 2), has been calibrated using a water manometer. The acquisition of the voltage values of the transducer was done using the NI 9205, storing 17800 samples per calibration point.

The uncertainty on the calibration is affected by the following contributions,

- For the pressure:
 - Type B uncertainty due to the reading limit values of the water manometer graduated scale, corresponding to 0.1mmHg:

$$\delta P_{manometer} = \frac{0.1 \times 9.8066}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.6 Pa$$

- Type B uncertainty due to the pressure transducer, equal to 1% of the maximum readable value (0.3 to 3.0 psi);
- Type A uncertainty related to the calibration error of the fitting of the voltage and the pressure measurements: $\delta V_{fitting}$

hence:

$$\delta p = \sqrt{\delta p_{manometer}^2 + \delta p_{transducer}^2 + \delta p_{calibration}^2}$$

- For the voltage:
 - Type A uncertainty due to the number of samples acquired:

$$\delta V_{samples} = \frac{1.96 \times std(V)}{\sqrt{N}} [V]$$

where the factor 1.96 stands for the factor related to a T-student error distribution in a confidence interval of 95%;

- Type B uncertainty due to the NI acquisition card electronic accuracy, equal to 1% of the full scale (10 V).

Hence:

$$\delta V = \sqrt{\delta V_{samples}^2 + \delta V_{NI}^2}$$

Figure 38a shows the calibration curve obtained for one of the channels of the pressure transducer with a membrane of a maximum pressure of 0.3 psi, with the error bars indicating the uncertainty limits on each point for both the pressure and the voltage.

At this point, the uncertainty of the pressure has been fitted to the values of pressure acquired for the calibration, to obtain a dependence law between the two variables to be applied for the pressure drop measurements in the test section. The fitted law is a second order polynomial curve. The uncertainty on the total pressure drop considers contribution of the uncertainty of each channel of the pressure transducer:

$$\delta(\Delta p_{tot}) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \delta(\Delta p_i^2)$$

Figure 38b shows an example of the error bars on the total pressure drop obtained for the Aluminum sample with this membrane. The results for the Inconel module are reported in Fig. xx.

(a) Calibration of one of the five channels of the pressure transducer

(b) Total pressure drop for the Aluminum: error bars

Figure 39: Uncertainty analysis pressure transducer

The mean uncertainty obtained on these measurements with a membrane of maximum acceptable pressure of 0.3 psi is equal to ± 218.4 Pa, in a confidence interval of 95%. The mean uncertainties associated to all the membranes are listed below (Table 10):

Max pressure accepted by the membrane	Uncertainty (Pa)
2070	±218.4
5500	±556.0
10 340	±1036.6
20 680	±2069.6

Table 10: Pressure uncertainties associated to all the membranes

The total pressure drop is depending on the mass flow rate of the air flowing in the test section. The uncertainty on its value is described below.

6.2. Mass flow rate

The mass flow rate is regulated using three rotameters. Each of them has been calibrated using a counter of volume of air and registering the value of volume variation ΔV in a certain interval of time (t). The mass flow rate is obtained as:

$$\dot{m} = \frac{\Delta V \rho}{t}$$

The calibration law relates this value to the height indicated by the oat on the graduated scale of the tempered metered tube of the rotameter.

In this case the uncertainty on the level of air in the rotameter is merely dependent on the instrument and it is a type B uncertainty, expressed as:

$$\delta H = \frac{0.1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

The uncertainty on the mass flow is more complex to obtain as it is a function of the contributions of the uncertainty of different properties. From the equation of the mass flow rate, it is possible to use the Taylor expansion model to estimate this uncertainty:

$$\delta \dot{m}_{definition} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial V} \delta V\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial t} \delta t\right)^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho}{t} \delta V\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V \rho}{t^2} \delta t\right)^2}$$

where $\delta V = 0.01/\sqrt{3}m^3$ and $\delta t = 1/\sqrt{3}s$, associated with the instrument reading limits. These contributions, together with the one due to the error associated with fitting of the calibration curve (Fig. 39), represent the total uncertainty on the mass flow rate:

$$\delta\dot{m} = \sqrt{(\delta\dot{m}_{definition})^2 + (\delta\dot{m}_{calibr})^2}$$

Figure 40: Calibration curve of one rotameter with error bars

6.3. Uncertainty of the hot wire velocity measurements

The uncertainty analysis on the velocity measured with the hot-wire anemometer depends on the entire measurement chain used from the calibration to the measurements themselves.

First, the probe has been calibrated in the potential core of an air jet, whose pressure was monitored using a pressure transducer. From these data of pressure, applying Bernoulli equation, it is possible to retrieve the velocity of the flow as:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta p}{\rho}}$$

where ρ is the flow density, retrieved acquiring the ow temperature using a thermocouple type K.

Hence, the sources of uncertainty coming from the calibration procedure are related to the calibration of the pressure transducer ($\delta(\Delta p)$) done using a water manometer and the hot-wire probe calibration. In the former case, the analysis is the same of the one explained in

§6.1, with the difference that each pressure value has been fitted in the calibration curve with one single correspondent value of voltage, read on the display of a digital voltmeter. This means that there is no error associated with the number of samples of acquisition.

Concerning the hot wire probe calibration, the uncertainty on the velocity calibration law depends on:

- the propagation of the uncertainty of the different properties the velocity depends on, as defined in the equation of the flow velocity above. It yields:

$$\delta u_{HW} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial v_{HW}}{\partial \Delta p} \delta(\Delta p)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v_{HW}}{\partial \rho} \delta \rho\right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\rho \Delta p} (\delta(\Delta p))^2 + \frac{\Delta p}{2\rho^3} (\delta \rho)^2}$$

where $\delta \rho$ is obtained from the application of the Taylor polynomial expansion to the ideal gas law $\rho = \frac{RT}{p}$:

$$\delta \rho = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} \delta p\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \delta T\right)^2}$$

With $\delta T = \mp 1.96 \frac{sdt(T)}{\sqrt{N}}$ and $\delta p = \mp 1.96 \frac{sdt(p)}{\sqrt{N}}$ and $N=30$ samples.

- the uncertainty due to the fitting law of the calibration of the velocity with the correspondent voltage output values of the probe $\delta u_{HW,calibration}$.

hence:

$$\delta u_{HW,total} = \sqrt{\delta u_{HW}^2 + \delta u_{HW,calibration}^2}$$

On the other hand, the uncertainty on the correspondent values of voltage depends only on two contributions:

- the number of samples chosen for the acquisition, equal to 30;
- the voltage NI card electronic accuracy, equal to 1% of the full scale (10V).

It yields:

$$\delta V = \sqrt{\delta V_{random}^2 + \delta V_{NI}^2} = \sqrt{\left(1.96 \frac{sdt(V)}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{0.01 \times 10}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2}$$

The global uncertainty on the velocity is fitted with the velocity data set to retrieve the coefficients of the uncertainty law to apply to the measurements (Fig. 40a) [20]. At this point, the uncertainty on the velocity profile measurements with the hot wire is obtained considering the combination of different sources of uncertainty:

- the type A uncertainty due to the calibration law ($\delta u_{HW,total}$);
- the type A uncertainty related to the number of acquired samples, equal to 750000 (δu_{random});
- the type B uncertainty related to an eventual misalignment of the probe in the experimental set-up after the calibration. This contribution is stochastic and can be expressed as :

$$\delta u_{probe} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(1 - \cos \theta)$$

Usually the probe is located with an uncertainty of $\Delta\theta=1^\circ$ [15].

- type B uncertainty related to possible variation of the temperature during the acquisition of the measurements. In case of gas, this is usually expressed as:

$$\delta u_T = \frac{\Delta T}{273\sqrt{3}}$$

Where ΔT is usually imposed equal to 1°C [15].

The global uncertainty on the measured velocity profiles is calculated as:

$$\delta u = \sqrt{(\delta u_{HW,total})^2 + (\delta u_{random})^2 + (\delta u_{probe})^2 + (\delta u_T)^2}$$

Fig. 40b shows the velocity profile obtained for $m=5\text{ g/s}$ and the porous plate located at the exit section of the divergent, with the correspondent error bars.

(a) Uncertainty hot-wire fitted curve.

(b) Velocity profile with error bars.

Figure 41: Uncertainty analysis hot-wire

6.4. Uncertainty on temperature measurements

Temperature measurements can be done in a non-intrusive or intrusive way. In this project both the techniques have been exploited; in particular, the IR thermography for the detection of the temperature distribution on the bottom wall of the sample and the thermocouples for the direct measurements of the air temperature in different points of the test section.

6.4.1. Uncertainty on thermocouples measurements

Thermocouples type K have been exploited for the temperature measurements in the test section. It includes a total number of 23 probes to monitor the air temperature in different positions.

It is important to highlight that only the four thermocouples of the inlet thermocouples rake and the nine thermocouples of the outlet rake have been calibrated. It is recalled from §2.2. that the thermocouples were calibrated by using an ageing chamber Weiss WK L34/40. The reference temperature inside the chamber was acquired by mean of a PT100 probe of class 1/3 ($\pm 0.08^\circ\text{C}$ at 0°C) with a number model PL1/3M30-300 of omega. The signal from this probe was transferred to a NI9217 card for acquisition at a frequency of 10 Hz and for a duration of 20 s, for a total of 200 samples for each measurement. The exigence of using such a probe as reference is due to two main aspects:

- the sake of high precision temperature measurements, especially for the Inconel sample, where the temperature gradient along the samples are very low;
- the impossibility of performing a calibration in the oil bath. Indeed, the outlet thermocouple rake cannot be inserted in the oil bath as it could be damaged if the oil enters the small holes where the thermocouples are fixed.

Figure 42: Ageing chamber Weiss WK L34/40

The main sources of error during the calibration procedure come from:

- standard type B uncertainty related to the accuracy of the reference mercury thermometer (δT_{ref});
- standard type B uncertainty due to the NI card acquisition error on the cold junction equal to ± 1 °C (δT_{NI});
- standard type A uncertainty related to the number of samples acquired during the calibration for each temperature level (δT_{random});
- standard type A uncertainty related to the calibration curve fitting (δT_{cal}).

hence, the total uncertainty on the temperature measurement using thermocouples can be quantified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta T &= \sqrt{(\delta T_{ref})^2 + (\delta T_{NI})^2 + (\delta T_{random})^2 + (\delta T_{cal})^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.08}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 + \left(1.96 \frac{sdt(T)}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^2 + (\delta T_{cal})^2} \end{aligned}$$

The mean total uncertainty for each thermocouple has been retrieved to be equal to ± 0.6 °C within a confidence interval of 95%.

The air temperature at the inlet section of the CHX sample is determined as a mean of the values read by the four probes of the inlet rake:

$$T_{in,m} = \frac{T_{1,m} + T_{2,m} + T_{3,m} + T_{4,m}}{4}$$

Hence the uncertainty on this value is given by the contribution of the uncertainty of the single probes, applying the Taylor polynomial approach:

$$\delta(T_{in,m}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial T_{in,m}}{\partial T_{1,m}} \delta(T_{1,m})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_{in,m}}{\partial T_{2,m}} \delta(T_{2,m})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_{in,m}}{\partial T_{3,m}} \delta(T_{3,m})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_{in,m}}{\partial T_{4,m}} \delta(T_{4,m})\right)^2}$$

$$\delta(T_{in,m}) = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^4 (\delta T_i)^2}$$

This reduces the uncertainty on the mean to ± 0.3 °C in a confidence interval of 95%.

Figure 42 shows an example of the error bars on the measurement of the inlet mean temperature measurements for the Aluminum sample V1 for a mass flow range from 3 g/s to 20 g/s.

Figure 43: Inlet mean temperature with error bars for the Aluminum sample V1

6.4.2. Uncertainty IT camera measurements

The temperature distribution on the bottom wall of the CHX module was measured using the IR thermography. In particular, the uncertainty coming from this measurement derives from:

the uncertainty of the thermocouple used as reference for the calibration of the IR camera, the uncertainty of the calibration of the camera itself and the final uncertainty of the measurements.

To calibrate the IR camera it is necessary to have a thermocouple as reference. On the bottom of the channel, a thermocouple type K was glued and the sample heated for different temperature levels. The IR camera, placed at a distance of 0.335m from the sample, was used to record the temperature distribution on a small spot taken near the reference thermocouple. In this way, the calibration curve of the IR camera correlates the temperature read by the IR camera with the one obtained from the thermocouple.

However, this last measurement includes already all the uncertainty coming from the calibration of the reference thermocouples, executed in the oil bath using the same procedure described for the inlet rake. The only difference was that the thermocouple was placed very near the bulb of the mercury thermometer to reduce any eventual difference induced by a non-uniform temperature distribution in the oil bath.

The uncertainty on the IR camera comes from different contributions:

- standard type A uncertainty related to the number of images acquired for each calibration point, equal to 30 (acquisition frequency of 1 Hz for 30 s): δT_{random} ;
- standard type A uncertainty associated with the reference thermocouple (δT_{tc});
- standard type A uncertainty derived from the fitting of the calibration law of the IR camera ($\delta T_{cal,IR}$);
- standard type B uncertainty associated to accuracy of the IR camera FLIR A655sc equal to the 2% of the reading temperature (δT_{camera}).

hence, the total uncertainty is:

$$\delta T_{IR,tot} = \sqrt{\delta T_{random}^2 + \delta T_{tc}^2 + \delta T_{cal,IR}^2 + \delta T_{camera}^2}$$

The fitting of this uncertainty with the calibration data of the IR camera gives the coefficients used for the determination of the uncertainty on measurements on the CHX sample, considering the additional contribution of the random error associated with the number of images acquired for each measurement, equal to 200. It yields:

$$\delta T_{IR,meas} = \sqrt{\delta T_{IR,random}^2 + \delta T_{IR,tot}^2} = \sqrt{\left(1.96 \frac{sdt(T_{IR})}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^2 + \delta T_{IR,tot}^2}$$

Figure 43a shows the calibration curve obtained for the IR camera and in Fig. 43b there is the plot of the mean temperature along the channel for the case of Aluminum and a mass flow of

5 g/s, with the error bars associated to the measurements. The mean uncertainty associated with the calibration is equal to ± 0.81 °C in a confidence interval of 95%. For the measurements it is in mean equal to ± 1.4 °C in a confidence interval of 95%, considering 200 images stored for each acquisition. It is important to emphasize that the IR measurements can be affected by additional errors classified as errors of methods and error associated to the electronic path. The former error class includes an incorrect evaluation of both the object emissivity and the ambient radiation. The influence of the radiation emitted by the ambient grows if the emissivity of the object is low, as a consequence, to reduce this effect, the sample bottom surface has been painted black and its emissivity fixed equal to 0.9 in the FLIR camera software used for the acquisition. The ambient radiation, in this case, has been considered negligible as the distance between the object and the camera is less than one meter.

The errors associated with the electronic path can depend on the detector noise, the instability of the cooling system, the fluctuations of the electronic systems, etc... and they are usually quantified below $\pm 1\%$ for low temperature ranges [13].

(a) Calibration curve of the IR camera

(b) Mean velocity profile along the Aluminum sample for $m=5\text{g/s}$ and $Q=130\text{W}$ with error bounds

Figure 44: Uncertainty analysis IR camera

6.5. Uncertainty on temperature measurements

In this section the uncertainty on the convective heat transfer coefficient is discussed. The formula of the convective heat transfer coefficient defines it as dependent on other properties, hence the total uncertainty associated with h is depending each uncertainty contribution of the single properties this coefficient is function of. The standard uncertainty

of h is retrieved applying the Taylor series polynomial expansion method, starting from its definition:

$$h_{conv} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{air}}{A_{exch}\Delta T_{LM}}$$

Where:

$$\Delta T_{LM} = \frac{T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}}{\ln\left(\frac{T_t - T_{air,in}}{T_t - T_{air,out}}\right)} = \frac{T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}}{\ln(X)}$$

And:

$$T_t = T_s - \frac{\dot{Q}_{joule}}{A_{res}} \left(\frac{t_{wall}}{k_m} \right)$$

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta h &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial h_{conv}}{\partial \dot{Q}_{air}} \delta \dot{Q}_{air}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial h_{conv}}{\partial A_{exch}} \delta A_{exch}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial h_{conv}}{\partial \Delta T_{LM}} \delta \Delta T_{LM}\right)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{A_{exch}\Delta T_{LM}} \delta \dot{Q}_{air}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{air}}{A_{exch}^2 \Delta T_{LM}} \delta A_{exch}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{air}}{A_{exch}\Delta T_{LM}^2} \delta \Delta T_{LM}\right)^2} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\dot{Q}_{air} = k_1 \dot{Q}_{joule} = k_1 Vi$$

$$A_{exch} = k_2 A_{res} = k_2 dl$$

Thus:

$$\delta \dot{Q}_{air} = \sqrt{(k_1 V \delta i)^2 + (k_1 i \delta V)^2}$$

$$\delta A_{exch} = \sqrt{(k_2 d \delta l)^2 + (k_2 d \delta l)^2}$$

with i and V respectively the current and the voltage associated to the Joule power provided by the power supplier, and d and l the dimensions of the base of the CHX module.

$\delta \Delta T_{LM}$ is obtained the same way by applying the Taylor series polynomial expansion method to its definition:

$$\delta \Delta T_{LM} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_{air,out}} \delta T_{air,out}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_{air,in}} \delta T_{air,in}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_t} \delta T_t\right)^2}$$

Where:

$$\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_{air,out}} = \frac{\ln(X) - (T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}) \times \frac{1}{T_t - T_{air,out}}}{\ln(X)^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_{air,in}} = \frac{-\ln(X) - (T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}) \times \frac{-1}{T_t - T_{air,in}}}{\ln(X)^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \Delta T_{LM}}{\partial T_t} = \frac{-(T_{air,out} - T_{air,in}) \times \left(\frac{1}{T_t - T_{air,in}} - \frac{1}{T_t - T_{air,out}} \right)}{\ln(X)^2}$$

$\delta T_{air,out}$ and $\delta T_{air,in}$ are developed before in 6.4.1. δT_t is derived considering its equation above, and it yields to:

$$\delta T_t = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial T_t}{\partial T_s} \delta T_s \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_t}{\partial \dot{Q}_{joule}} \delta \dot{Q}_{joule} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_t}{\partial A_{res}} \delta A_{res} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_t}{\partial t_{wall}} \delta t_{wall} \right)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(\delta T_s)^2 + \left(\frac{t_{wall}}{A_{res} k_m} \delta \dot{Q}_{joule} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{joule} t_{wall}}{A_{res}^2 k_m} \delta A_{res} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{joule}}{A_{res} k_m} \delta t_{wall} \right)^2}$$

with δT_s uncertainty on the measurements of the thermocouples placed under the heating plate and t_{wall} the thickness of the upper wall of the CHX sample and δt_{wall} the uncertainty associated to its measurements.

Figure 45 shows the results obtained for h for both the material, including the error bars. The maximum values of uncertainty for the Aluminium and the Inconel are respectively $\pm 10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and $\pm 2.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, in a confidence interval of 95%.

(a) Aluminum CHX module

(b) Inconel CHX module

Figure 45: Uncertainties to the convective heat transfer coefficient

7. Reference

- [1] Y.A. Cengel and J.M. Cimbala. *Fluid Mechanics: Fundamentals and Applications*. McGraw-Hill series in mechanical engineering. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 2006.
- [2] Giovanni Maria Carlomagno and Gennaro Cardone. *Infrared thermography for convective heat transfer measurements*. Experiments in fluids, 49(6):1187-1218, 2010.
- [3] Alexander Karel Muntjewerf. *Laminar flow heat transfer in the thermal entrance region of at and profiled ducts*. 1969.
- [4] Jean-Marie Buchlin and Léon Bolle. *Advanced Heat Exchangers*: September 16-20, 2002. Rhode Saint Gennèse, Belgium, 2002.
- [5] Bahman Zohuri. *Compact heat exchangers*. Springer Science+Business Media, New York, NY, 2016.
- [6] Stimpson, C. K., Snyder, J. C., Thole, K. A., and Mongillo, D., 2015, *Roughness Effects on Flow and Heat Transfer for Additively Manufactured Channels*, ASME J. Turbomach, 138(5), p. 051008.
- [7] Stone K. M., Vanka S. P., 1996, *Review of literature on Heat Transfer Enhancement in Compact Heat Exchangers*, Air Conditioning and Refrigeration Center, University of Illinois.
- [8] Ramesh K. Shah and Duan P. Sekuli. *Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, USA, July 2003.
- [9] Hao Peng, Xiang Ling, and Juan Li. *Performance investigation of an innovative offset strip fin arrays in compact heat exchangers*. Energy conversion and management, 80:287-297, 2014.
- [10] Ki-Baik Lee and Young-Kil Kwon. *Flow and thermal field with relevance to heat transfer enhancement of interrupted-plate heat exchangers*. Experimental Heat Transfer, An International Journal, 5(2):83-100, 1992.
- [11] Guannan Xi, Yoshimichi Hagiwara, Kenjiro Suzuki, and Tetsuo Kaneda. *Effect of fin thickness on ow and heat-transfer characteristics of fin arrays: an offset-fin array in the low reynolds number range*. Heat transfer. Japanese research, 21(1):1-19, 1992.
- [12] Kulkarni, V., Sahoo, N., & Chavan, S. D. (2011). *Simulation of honeycomb–screen combinations for turbulence management in a subsonic wind tunnel*. Journal of wind engineering and industrial aerodynamics, 99(1), 37-45
- [13] Waldemar Minkina and Sebastian Dudzik. *Infrared thermography: errors and uncertainties*. John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [14] Stephanie Bell. Measurement good practice guide no. 11 (issue 2). *A beginner's guide to uncertainty of measurement*. National Physical Laboratory Teddington, Middlesex, United Kingdom, 2001.

-
- [15] F Jorgenson. *How to measure turbulence with hot-wire anemometers (a practical guide)*, 2002. Dantec Dynamics, Skovlunde, Denmark.
- [16] Ascione F. Conrozier A., Sakly A., Planquart P., Hugo J. M., Laboureur D., *Aerothermal Characterization of a Compact Heat Exchanger Element by Additive*, 2020, Aerospace Europe Conference.
- [17] Francesco Baldani and Walter Bosschaerts. *Design of a hot-wire rake for measurements in temperature-varying flow fields*. Energy Procedia, 85:35-43, 2016.
- [18] Churchill, S. W., 1977, *Friction factor equations spans all fluid-flow ranges.*, Chem. Eng., 91
- [19] Barbin, A. R., & Jones, J. B. (1963). *Turbulent flow in the inlet region of a smooth pipe*. Journal of Basic Engineering, 85(1), 29-33.
- [20] Savas Yavuzkurt. *A guide to uncertainty analysis of hot-wire data*. ASME, Transactions, Journal of Fluids Engineering, 106(2):181-186, 1984.
- [21] Han, J. C., Zhang, Y. M., and Lee, C. P., 1991, *Augmented Heat Transfer in Square Channels With Parallel, Crossed, and V-Shaped Angled Ribs*, ASME J. Heat Transfer, 113(3), pp. 590–596.
- [22] Kandlikar, S. G., Schmitt, D., Carrano, A. L., and Taylor, J. B., 2005, *Characterization of Surface Roughness Effects on Pressure Drop in Single-Phase Flow in Minichannels*, Phys. Fluids, 17(10), p. 100606.
- [23] Colebrook, C. F.; White, C. M. (3 August 1937). *Experiments with Fluid Friction in Roughened Pipes*. Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences. 161 (906): 367–381.